

Globalashuv sharoitida suv ob'yektlari ifloslanishining monitoring

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Dolzarbliqi: Ochiq suv havzalarining chiqindi suvlari bilan ifloslanishi aholi o'rtasida turli yuqumli kasalliklarning kelib chiqishiga va tarqalishiga sabab bo'lmoqda. Ayniqsa qorin tifi, paratiflar, salmonellyoz, ichburug', virusli gepatitning "A" turi, vabo va boshqalar. O'tkir yuqumli kasalliklar ifloslangan suv orqali tez va ommaviy tarqalish xususiyatiga ega.

Maqsad: suv ob'yektlarida suvning fizik-kimyoviy va mikrobiologik ko'rsatkichlarini laborator tekshirish natijatalari asosida suv sifatini gigiyenik baholashdan iborat.

Usullari: 2020-2022 yillar dinamikasida suv resurslarining suv sifatini toifalar bo'yicha ifloslanish holati ma'lumotlari retrospektiv taxlili o'tkazildi. Olingan natijalar sanitariya qoidalari va me'yorlarida belgilangan gigiyenik me'yorlar bilan taqqoslandi va ifloslanish darajasi gigiyenik baholandi.

Natijalar: Kuzatuv yili davomida 2-chi toifa suv ob'yektlaridan olingan namunalarning umumiy soni 1881 ta (100%) bo'lib, ulardan 307 tasi (16,3%) gigiyenik talablarga mos kelmaganligi aniqlandi. Har ikkala suv ob'yektlarning suvining tekshirish natijalarini tahlil qiladigan bo'lsak kuzatuv yilida 2-chi toifa suv ob'yektlarining suvining sifat ko'rsatkichlari 1-chi toifa suv ob'yektlari suv sifatiga nibatan ko'proq ifloslangan.

Kalit so'zlari: aholi, globalashuv, suv ob'yektlari, ifloslanish, chiqindi suv, yuqumli kasalliklar, tashqi muhit, xavf omili.

Мониторинг загрязнения водных объектов в условиях глобализации

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Актуальность: Загрязнение открытых водоемов сточными водами вызывает возникновение и распространение среди населения различных инфекционных заболеваний. Особенно брюшной тиф, паратифы, сальмонеллез, вирусный гепатит «А», холера и др. Острые инфекционные заболевания характеризуются быстрым и массовым распространением через загрязненную воду.

Цель: гигиеническая оценка качества воды по результатам лабораторных исследований физико-химических и микробиологических показателей воды водных объектов.

Методы: В динамике за 2020-2022 годов проведен ретроспективный анализ данных о состоянии загрязнения водных ресурсов и качестве воды по категориям. Полученные результаты сравнивали с гигиеническими нормами, установленными санитарными правилами и стандартами, и дали гигиеническую оценку уровню загрязнения воды.

Результаты: за годы мониторинга общее количество проб, отобранных из водных объектов 2-й категории, составило 1881 (100%), из них 307 (16,3%) не соответствовали гигиеническим требованиям. При анализе результатов обследования воды обоих водных объектов, установлено, что в год наблюдения показатели качества воды водных объектов 2-й категории загрязнены сильнее, чем качество воды водных объектов 1-й категории.

Ключевые слова: население, глобализация, водные объекты, загрязнение, сточные воды, инфекционные заболевания, внешняя среда, фактор риска.

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Water pollution monitoring of water bodies under globalization

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Relevance: Opollution of the catchment basins with waste water causes the origin and spread of various infectious diseases among the population. Especially typhoid fever, paratyphus, salmonellosis, gonorrhoea, viral hepatitis "A" type, cholera, etc. Acute infectious diseases are characterized by rapid and massive spread through contaminated water.

Aim: hygienic assessment of water quality based on the results of laboratory studies of physical, chemical and microbiological indicators of water in water bodies.

Methods: retrospective analysis of the data on the state of pollution of water resources by categories was conducted in the dynamics of 2020-2022. The obtained results were compared with the hygienic standards set in the sanitary rules and regulations, and the level of pollution was evaluated hygienically.

Results: During the monitoring year, the total number of samples taken from the 2nd category water bodies was 1881 (100%), of which 307 (16.3%) did not meet hygienic requirements. If we analyze the results of the water inspection of both water bodies, in the observation year, the water quality indicators of the 2nd category water bodies are more polluted than the water quality of the 1st category water bodies.

Keywords: population, globalization, water bodies, pollution, waste water, infectious diseases, external environment, risk factor.

1. Introduction

Globalization of climate change, continuation of the desertification process on a global scale as a result, the risk of water shortage is becoming more and more serious. Water shortage is evident in Central Asian countries, especially in the Republic of Uzbekistan [2,5]. Therefore, taking measures to eliminate the threatening danger is the priority direction of managing the use of water resources in our republic. At the same time, pollution of open water bodies with waste water causes the origin and spread of various infectious diseases among the population. Typhoid fever, paratyphus, salmonellosis, cholera, viral hepatitis type "A", cholera and a number of other acute infectious diseases are characterized by rapid and massive spread through polluted water [1,4,7]. These diseases are caused by bacteria and viruses that are more resistant to the external environment. The above-mentioned diseases are collectively called acute intestinal diseases, and their prevalence is 50-70% of acute intestinal infections among young children in our country. Acute intestinal diseases cause the death of approximately 5 million young children in the world every year. In the development of these diseases, especially environmental objects, in particular, water, food products and dirty hands in life, household items (dishes, dishes, etc.) play an important role [3,6].

2. Methods and materials

In order to fulfill the goal set before us, a retrospective analysis of the data on the state of pollution of water resources by categories was conducted in the dynamics of 2020-2022. The obtained results were compared with the hygienic standards set in the sanitary rules and regulations, and the level of pollution was evaluated hygienically.

3. Results

Based on the above, we conducted a laboratory test of the water quality of water bodies in the places where the population uses water and obtained the following results. In 2020, a total of 90 (100%) samples were taken from water bodies of the 1st category, of which 8 (8.9%) did not meet hygienic requirements (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Water quality status of water bodies in places of water use by the population (water bodies of type 1 in 2020).

Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Water and Water Use" The following has been established: "The condition of maintaining the health of the population and first meeting the requirements for drinking water and domestic needs during the placement, design, construction and commissioning of new and renovated enterprises, structures and other objects that affect the state of water, as well as during the introduction of new technological processes it is necessary to ensure the rational use of water. Therefore, in the hygienic evaluation of the level of pollution of the uv pool, their classification also plays an important role. For this reason, we also conducted water quality laboratory testing of water bodies of the 2nd category and obtained the following results: the total number of samples was 133 (100%), of which 20 samples (15.0%) did not meet hygienic requirements (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Water quality status of water bodies in places of water use by the population (water bodies of the 2nd category in 2020).

Nowadays, one of the main tasks facing humanity is keeping water resources clean and using them wisely. Because ensuring food security is an important factor of socio-economic sustainable development. Ensuring human health, environmental safety, and the well-being of the population depends on water supply. The result of observations in 2021 is as follows: the total number of samples was 719 (100%), of which 12 samples (1.6%) did not meet hygienic requirements (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3 State of water bodies in places of water use of the population (2021 type 1 water bodies).

Open water resourcescontrolling the quality of water, preventing the spillage of oil and other pollutants into water bodies, establishing control over the use of water by enterprises, controlling the

biological, chemical and bacteriological condition of sources that provide drinking water to the population, these will be of inestimable importance in the protection of water resources in the future. Based on the following, we are especially in the dynamics of the years in 2021 at the condition of water bodies in water use areas is 2nd type water bodies. The results of the observations are as follows: the total number of samples is 2045 (100%), of which 44 samples (2.1%) did not meet hygienic requirements (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Status of water bodies in places of water use by the population (2021 type 2 water bodies).

Improper use of water, its pollution, low quality and lack of it cause a number of problems. These include: a) contamination of many running waters and underground waters, insufficient supply of drinking water to the population. In general, one-third of the country's population consumes drinking water that does not meet state standards, and irrigation is not used sparingly. The complexity of the water resources management system is characterized not only by the fact that it consists of a large number of infrastructures, but also by their interconnectedness. In 2022 at the condition of water bodies in water use areas is 1st type water bodies. The results of the observations are as follows: the total number of samples is 409 (100%), of which 16 samples (3.9%) did not meet hygienic requirements (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5. State of the water body in the places of water use of the population (water bodies of the 1st category in 2022).

Irrigated agriculture is the main source of surface water pollution, polluting 78% of the total, industry 18%, communal economy 4%. Almost half of the water flowing in the reservoir falls into the republic's water supply networks and water basins, municipal and industrial effluents. In 2022 at the condition of water bodies in water use areas is 2nd type water bodies. The results of the observations are as follows: the total number of samples is 1881 (100%), of which 307 samples (16.3%) did not meet hygienic requirements (Fig. 6).

Fig. 6. State of the water body in the places of water use of the population (water bodies of the 2nd category in 2022).

4. Discussion

As a result of the globalization of climate change and the continuation of the desertification process on a global scale, the risk of water shortage is becoming more and more serious. Water shortage is evident in the countries of Central Asia, especially in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Therefore, taking measures to eliminate the threatening danger is the priority direction of managing the use of water resources of our republic.

Analyzing the results of the inspection of the water of both water bodies, we found out that the water quality indicators of the 2nd category water bodies were more polluted than the water quality of the 1st category water bodies in the observation year. As we know, water bodies of the 2nd category are used for cultural and household purposes, which causes water-related infectious diseases among the population.

5. Conclusions

Based on the above, it can be concluded from the results of the analysis of the water of water bodies that in the year of observation, the water quality indicators of water bodies of the 2nd category are more polluted than the water quality of the water bodies of the 1st category. As we know, water bodies of the 2nd category are used for cultural and household needs, which causes the emergence of water-related infectious diseases among the population. In the prevention of acute intestinal infectious diseases, measures to eliminate the spread of microorganisms by household means are very important. It is necessary not to pollute open water bodies with various wastes, and not to bathe in unmarked water bodies.

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